

INTERFACE AND MATRIX OPTIMIZATION
IN
SINTERED CERAMIC COMPOSITES

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Summary

The A.C.K.⁺ analysis, previously used to explain the mechanical behavior of composites of glass-ceramic reinforced by SiC fibers (COMPGLASS from UTRC) (1), is employed here as a methodological tool in the optimization of new ceramic composites.

In the first section, this method of analysis is briefly reviewed. Its application is illustrated through the presentation of critical stress diagrams for two realistic composite systems (carbone/glass and SiC Whiskers/glass-ceramic).

The second section presents the investigation of two new systems, based on infiltration and pressure-less sintering of very fine α -alumina powder with parallel fibers of FP Dupont alumina and Nicalon SiC. The processing of these system is described and properties of the resultant composites are presented and discussed :

- physical characteristics and stress-strain diagrams,
- mechanical characteristics of the alumina matrix as a function of sintering temperature,
- their critical stress diagrams and
- the values of important microstructural parameters.

Finally, the mechanical behavior is analysed based on these microstructural and physical parameters. The analysis points out both the advantages and limitations of this methodology and emphasizes the opportunities for further progress that the relatively simple processing techniques developed during the course of this investigation make possible.

1 - Introduction

Development of ceramic matrix composites depends largely upon the understanding of their fracture mechanics. Currently, a large effort to increase this understanding is underway since it has become more and more evident that to improve the mechanical behavior of these system the fabrication process must be based on a knowledge of the fracture mechanisms. Previous work, with my colleagues at NRL, on the tensile behavior of the unidirectional composite

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COMPGLASS (SiC/LAS from UTRC) indicated that the ACK analysis (1) could yield useful insights on the behavior. This analysis provides an interesting model for projecting the critical stress level of brittle matrix composites.

The present investigation uses this model to compute graphical representations of such composite systems giving the critical tensile stress as a function of the volume fraction of fibers and the interfacial shear strength. It applies this model to the development of new alumina matrix composites with various levels of porosity. It describes the fabrication of these composites by high pressure slip casting with slurries of very fine powders. Finally, it proposes an analytical method for optimizing the fabrication process.

2 - Critical Stress Diagrams of Unidirectional Composites

The ACK analysis (2) is based on an energy conservation balance to determine the tensile stress at which the first cracks appear in the matrix. This model, in addition to the fiber and matrix properties ($E_f, \phi_f, E_m, \gamma_m$), also requires terms describing the composite : the volume fraction of fibers (V_f) and the interfacial shear strength (τ_o).

In such composites, to develop the matrix microcracking, the energetic balance between the work done by the applied stresses, the strain energy in the material and the fracture energy of the matrix is modified by two additional terms : the strain energy of fibers and the interfacial friction work of extracting the fibers from the matrix. The net effect is to increase the strain at which the matrix cracks in the composite. This strain is given by the following expression :

$$\epsilon_{mu}^* = \left[\frac{24\tau_o \gamma_m E_f V_f^2}{E_c E_m^2 \phi_f V_m} \right]^{1/3}$$

The corresponding stress at which the non linear behavior begins, called the critical tensile stress, is :

$$\sigma_{cni}^* = \epsilon_{mu}^* E_c$$

Using this analysis, it is now possible to obtain a representation of the mechanical behavior of a given composite system for which the fiber and matrix data are known. Variations of the critical tensile stress are described by only two parameters :

- the volume fraction of fibers and
- the fiber-matrix interfacial shear strength.

Figure 1 presents such a diagram for the unidirectional COMPGLASS system for which the LAS matrix and Nicalon SiC fiber properties are given in table 1.

Fig. 1 : Critical stress diagram of the unidirectional COMPGLOSS system

Table 1 : Fiber and matrix properties

	Fibers properties	Matrix properties
σ_u (MPa)	2060	120
E (GPa)	206	75
ϵ_u	10 10 ⁻³	1.6 10 ⁻³
α (°C ⁻¹)	3 10 ⁻⁶	1.45 10 ⁻⁶
ϕ_f (μ m)	12	
γ_m (J/m ²)		25

For this model the critical stress does not depend upon the state of thermal stress if σ^*_{cni} is at least equal to

$$\sigma^*_c = \epsilon_{mu} E_c + E_f V_f \Delta\alpha\Delta T$$

Otherwise, the thermal stresses themselves should result in failure of the matrix. This thermal stress could be represented in the diagram by a straight line, if

it were assumed that the difference between the two thermal expansion coefficients inside the process temperature range is constant. The critical stress will have an upper limit given by the ultimate stress of the reinforcement (σ_{fu}).

To illustrate these points, two theoretical diagrams have been computed. They represent, first, the aligned SiC whiskers/LAS system (Fig. 2), and secondly, the HM carbon fiber/LAS system (Fig. 3). They have been obtained with the LAS properties given in table 1 and fiber properties given in table 2.

Table 2 : SiC whisker (3) and HM carbon fiber (4) properties

	SIC whiskers	HM carbon fibers
σ_{fu} (MPa)	9500	2350
E_f (GPa)	700	350
ϵ_{fu}	12.5 10 ⁻³	6 10 ⁻³
L_f (mm)	5	
\varnothing_f (μm)	0.5	7

Fig. 2 : Critical stress diagram of the aligned SiC whiskers/LAS system

Fig. 3 : Critical stress diagram of HM carbon fibers/LAS system

In the first system, the whiskers are assumed to be aligned with a length L_f greater than the critical length L_c . This condition is :

$$\tau_o > \frac{\sigma_{fu} \phi_f}{4L_f}$$

Taking $L_f = 5 \text{ mm}$, τ_o would have to be at least, 0.24 MPa to satisfy this condition. The lower limit of the validity range of this condition is represented in the diagram by the iso- τ_o curve ($\tau_o = .24 \text{ MPa}$) (see Fig. 2).

Thus, these diagrams indicate :

- the critical stress level that the system is able to reach as a function of V_f and τ_o ,
- the maximum strength level possible before the collapse of the reinforcement ($\sigma_c V_f$)
- the maximum α_{cnl} value for a given V_f .
- the need or not to modify the interface, comparing the desired τ_o to ultimate strength of the matrix, and
- the relative level of the residual stresses.

In the following section, with the aid of this model, the analysis and optimization of the fabrication process for alumina matrix/aligned ceramic fiber systems are presented.

3 - Alumina Matrix and Unidirectional Ceramic Fiber Composite Systems

1. Processing and morphology of the systems

The present investigation is based on the use of an alumina matrix obtained by the infiltration of a slurry of very fine powder through aligned fibers using a high pressure slip casting method. The four main steps of this process are given in fig. 4.

Fig. 4 : The four processing steps of these composites

- Two systems were fabricated in this way :
- FP Dupont alumina fibers/Sumitomo α -alumina AKP50
 - Nicalon SiC fibers/Sumitomo α -alumina AKP50

Component properties are presented in table 3.

Parameters	SiC fibers	FP fibers
σ_{fu} (MPa)	2060	1900
E_f (GPa)	206	380
ϵ_{fu}	10 10^{-3}	4.5 10^{-3}
α_f ($^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$)	3 10^{-6}	8.7 10^{-6}
\varnothing_f (μm)	12	20

Table 3 : Component properties of the two systems

Sumitomo AKP 50 Alumina

Purity	99,99
Phase	α (80%)
Mean size	0,2-0,3 μm
Specific area	12 m^2/g
2000 psi density	1,9

Dupont FP and Nicalon SiC fibers have been chosen, first for their thermostability and mechanical properties and secondly for their two different surface roughnesses which can modify physically the interfacial shear strength.

The AKP 50 Sumitomo α -alumina has been chosen, first for its high purity and cristallinity stabilized at high temperature, and secondly for its fine grain size which aids the infiltration in the fiber substrates and lowers the sintering temperatures.

The shrinkage of such matrices is shown in fig. 5. The presence of fibers impedes this shrinkage axially as well as radially. However, it has been shown previously (5), that for systems whose components have isotropic thermal coefficients, stress relaxation during sintering can allow shrinkage without cracking if the porosity is below a limit that depends upon the fiber volume fraction (V_f) and interfacial bond strength. This porosity depends mainly upon the sintering temperature which must be lower than the thermostability temperature of the reinforcement. For the most favorable conditions the highest temperature which does not result in a strength reduction of over 10% has been found to be :

- 1450°C for FP fibers and
- 1300°C for SiC fibers.

The difference in the thermal expansion coefficients of the components can lead to microcracking. This difference is quite large in the SiC/Al₂O₃ system.

The two systems presented here were identically prepared and sintered at three temperatures : 1025,1145 and 1240°C. To allow comparison of the experimental mechanical behavior with critical strength diagrams, we determine successively :

- physical properties of the composites : fiber volume fractions (V_f), densities (ρ_c), porosities (P_c) and matrix porosities (P_m),
- characteristics of the alumina as a function of the sintering temperature: porosity, Young's modulus (E_m), and fracture surface energy (γ_m).

2 - Physical and Mechanical Characteristics of the Composites

Physical Characteristics

The nature of the casting process allows the quantity of fibers and the volume of the mold used to find Vf.

The composite and matrix porosities (Pc and Pm) were deduced from apparent densities (ρ_c), immersion densities and the densities of the components (alumina : 3.95, SiC fibers : 2,7).

Fig. 5 : AKP50 Sumitomo alumina density and shrinkage during sintering

These data are summarized in table 4 below.

Table 4 : Physical characteristics of the composites

Sintering T°	FP/AKP 50 system			SiC/AKP 50 system				
	Vf %	ρ_c	ρ_m	Pm %	Vf %	ρ_c	ρ_m	Pm %
1025°C	38,3	2,72	1,94	50,9	19,1	2,42	2,35	40,4
1145°C	40,4	2,81	2,04	48,4	19,5	2,51	2,46	37,6
1240°C	40,7	3,0	2,35	40,6	19,8	2,59	2,56	35,1

Mechanical characterization

For each plate of composite (60 x 40 x 3 mm), 3 samples (60 x 12 x 2.7 mm) were used for 4 points flexure tests. A large L/e ratio (18.5) was used for these tests to ensure conditions close to pure tensile stress between the 2 internal supports during the linear loading range. The samples were loaded with a constant crosshead displacement rate of 0.5 mm/min. When possible, each test was conducted in 4 steps to examine the non linear behavior :

- loading through the linear range,
- unloading,
- reloading up to the maximum strength,
- unloading again.

Six stress/strain diagrams so obtained are presented in figs. 6 (FP/AKP 50 composites) and 7 (SiC/AKP 50 composites). Through these diagrams, 3 main mechanical parameters can be found :

- the critical stress for matrix cracking, σ_{cnl} ,
- the initial Young's modulus, $E_{co Exp.}$ and,
- the maximum stress, σ_{max} .

3 - Estimation of Matrix Mechanical Properties as a Function of Sintering Temperature

Young's modulus and the fracture surface energy of the matrix used to analyse the mechanical behavior of the composites were determined experimentally by indentation methods on samples of the alumina used in the composites, but without fibers. These characteristics were extrapolated to higher porosities using the following general expression :

$$K = K_0 \exp(-bP)$$

with K : property
K₀: property at zero porosity
P : porosity
b : coefficient

Vickers indentations were used to evaluate the hardness (Hv) and the critical stress intensity factor (K_{Ic}) (6), with Young's modulus (E_m) obtained on alumina sintered at 1170 and 1275°C. These measurements were used to deduce modulus and fracture surface energy expressions of the form given above, which are also given in the table. Their use in the matrix porosity range of the composites (35 < P < 50%) is an approximation which can be evaluated by comparing, for example, the experimental and theoretical initial Young's modulus of the composites.

To estimate the matrix ultimate strains, an expression from the literature (8) relating ultimate strength to porosity was chosen. This expression :

$$\sigma_m = 278 \exp(-5.3P) \quad (\sigma_m \text{ in MPa})$$

was developed for an alumina of grain size close to that measured in these composites (.5 < G < 1 μm) and for a porosity range (0 < P < 60%) which includes the matrix porosity levels.

Fig. 6 : Stress/strain diagrams of FP Dupont/Alumina AKP50 Composites

Fig. 7 : Stress/strain diagrams of SiC Nicalon/Alumina AKP50 Composites

The ultimate strain is given by the ratio of the expressions for σ_m and E_m . The exponents of the two expressions are equal (see table 5), therefore the ultimate strain is independent of the porosity and equal to $.58 \times 10^{-3}$.

Table 5 : Estimation of mechanical characteristics of AKP50 alumina

Alumina	T° frittage (°C)	ρ_m g/cc	P %	Hv GPa	E/Hv	E_m GPa	K_{Ic} MPa \sqrt{m}	γ_m J/m ²
AKP50	1275	3,45	14	17,7	12,9	228,9	2,86	17,9
	1190	2,9	27	8,8	12,8	112,6	1,41	8,8
37 exp (-5,3P)								
475 exp (-5,3P)								
38,3 exp (-5,4P)								

4 - Critical Stress Diagrams of the Composites

The parameters used to calculate the critical stress of the two composites systems as a function of Vf and τ_0 , as defined in section 2, are given below :

- Young's moduli (E_m), fracture surface energies (γ_m), ultimate strains (ϵ_m) and strengths (σ_m) of the matrices were deduced from matrix developed in the previous section,

- Diameters (ϕ_f), Young's moduli (E_f), and ultimate strengths (σ_f) of analysis to be single valued,

- Fiber volume fractions (Vf) obtained in section 2 locate the working points along the abscissa of the diagrams,

- and finally, critical stresses ($\sigma_{cnl Ex.}$) and maximum stresses ($\sigma_{c max Ex.}$) from the experimental stress/strain diagrams locate the position of the composites along the stress axis.

These are summarized in table 6. In addition, the theoretical and experimental initial Young's modulus ($E_{co Th.}$ and $E_{co Ex.}$) are compared and the experimental critical strains ($\epsilon_{cnl Ex.}$) and the product $\epsilon_m \cdot E_{co Ex.}$, corresponding to the fracture strength of the composite in the linear analysis, are given.

Table 6 : Summary of microstructure parameters of the AKP50
alumina matrix composites

Parameters	Système FP/AKP50			Système SiC/AKP50		
	1025	1145	1240	1025	1145	1240
T° frittage(°C)	1025	1145	1240	1025	1145	1240
EmTh. (GPa)	32	36,5	55,2	55,8	64,8	74,3
γ mTh.(J/m ²)	2,4	2,8	4,3	4,2	5,1	5,8
ϵ mTh.(10 ⁻³)	0,58	0,58	0,58	0,58	0,58	0,58
σ mTh.(MPa)	18,7	21,4	32,3	32,6	37,9	43,5
Øf (µm)	20	20	20	12	12	12
Ef (GPa)	380	380	380	206	206	206
σ f (MPa)	1900	1900	1900	2060	2060	2060
Vf (%)	38,3	40,4	40,7	19,1	19,5	19,8
σ cnl Ex. (MPa)	335	186	187	195	120	80
ϵ mEco Ex. (MPa)	92	109	130	42,5	50,6	54,7
σ cmax Ex. (MPa)	423	215	137	217	243	365
Eco Th. (GPa)	165,3	175,3	187,4	84,5	92,3	100,4
Eco Ex. (GPa)	158,8	187,4	224	73,2	87,2	94,3
ϵ cnl Ex.(10 ⁻³)	2,1	1,0	0,6	2,7	1,4	0,85

Critical stresses diagrams of the FP/AKP50 and SiC/AKP50 composites computed from these data are presented in fig. 8 and fig. 9 respectively. The range of parameters for each system gives sufficiently small displacements of the curves of constant τ_0 that the 3 composites can be shown on the same diagram.

5 - Mechanical Behavior Analysis

Comparison of the experimental critical strain of composites (ϵ_{cnl} Ex. in table 6) and the estimated ultimate strain of matrices (ϵ_m Th.) indicates clearly that the fiber/matrix coupling phenomenon is operative in the 2 systems, particularly at the lowest sintering temperatures. In fact, the SiC/AKP50 composite sintered at 1025°C gives a critical strain 4.5 times higher than the ultimate matrix strain.

For the highest sintering temperatures (1240°C), the behavior of the 2 systems differ markedly :

- the FP/AKP50 composite shows no difference between the values of the critical stress, the maximum stress and the rupture stress ; this indicates either a strong fiber-matrix interfacial bond or an appreciable degradation of the fibers. Both possibilities would result in a transfiber, nondissipative rupture mode.

Fig. 8 : ACK diagrams of FP fiber/AKP50 matrix system

Fig. 9 : ACK diagrams of SiC fiber/AKP50 matrix system

- the SiC/AKP50 composite shows the largest gap between the critical stress (80MPa : relatively close to ϵ_m . Eco Ex.) and the maximum stress (365 MPa) ; this is a sign of a very weak interfacial bond giving a large compliance and a very energetic fracture mode.

This last comparison is completed by the more general one between the fracture modes of the 2 systems. The FP/AKP50 composites leave the linear domain by rupture if the fibers (sharp breaks in the stress/strain curves). In contrast, the SiC/AKP50 composites show a gradual curvature suggesting microcracking of the matrix. So, the fiber/matrix coupling phenomenon is not as effective in the first system as in the second. This strength limitation by fiber fracture can be represented in the critical stress diagram by a new $\sigma_f V_f$ line joining the origin to the experimental point (V_f, σ_{cni}) ; this is a method of estimating the new ultimate strength of fibers damaged during processing. More realistically, this strength can be bounded by the following limits :

$$\frac{\sigma_{cni} \text{ Ex.}}{V_f} < \sigma'_f < \frac{\sigma_{max} \text{ Ex.}}{V_f}$$

and so, the strength of the FP fibers, in the FP/AKP50 system, are estimated to be :

- 1025°C.....875 MPa $< \sigma'_f < 1104$ MPa
- 1145°C.....460 MPa $< \sigma'_f < 532$ MPa
- 1240°C.....336 MPa $< \sigma'_f < 336$ MPa

Due to this degradation, the levels of fiber/matrix interface strengths derived from the critical stress diagram of this system have no significance other than furnishing a lower limit.

However, the progressive nature of the damage observed for the SiC/AKP50 composite suggests that the levels of τ_o obtained from critical stress diagram are significant. These τ_o values are given in table 7 and compared with the theoretical ultimate strength of the matrices. The maximum stress recorded for each composite is also given.

Table 7 : Comparison between strengths of fiber/matrix interface and matrix strengths in the SiC/AKP50 system

$T^{\circ}f$ (°C)	τ_o (MPa)	σ_m Th. (MPa)	σ_{max} (MPa)
1025	40	32,6	217
1145	9	37,9	243
1240	3	43,5	365

This comparison shows similar values of the 2 strengths for the composite sintered at 1025°C. Nevertheless, contrary to the FP system, the SiC fibers show no

apparent damage and so the initial strain can occur without fiber fracture. The strength of the interface bonding decreases very rapidly with the sintering temperature whereas the matrix strength increases significantly, leading to the observed low critical stress for the composite sintered at 1240°C.

4 - Conclusions

The methodology, based on the ACK theory, used in this study to analyse the mechanical behavior of new ceramic matrix composites is very useful in understanding the limits of linear behavior in these systems. In addition to the critical fiber/matrix interfacial strength estimation, it allows detection and estimation of possible damage of the reinforcement in the composites during processing. Yet, for these kinds of systems, for which phenomena associated with sintering in the presence of fibers (impeded shrinkage, stress relaxations,...) are not well understood, the a priori prediction of behavior is not possible. Nevertheless, this approach can aid in process optimization. A reduced experimental program allows analysis of the critical fiber/matrix interfacial strength as a function of sintering temperature and Vf. Consequently, the linear domain of the system can be examined and thermal treatments modified to optimize this behavior.

In addition to illustrating the advantage of this analytical method for optimizing the ceramic matrix composites, this investigation underlines the technological possibilities of such sintered matrix systems. The processing technique is relatively simple, and the utilisation of very fine powders allows : first, efficient infiltration into small diameter fiber substrates and, secondly, sufficient sintering inside a temperature range in accordance with the thermostability of ceramic fibers. In spite of unfavorable shrinkage and thermal expansion strains which should, theoretically, develop during the processing, the mechanical behavior and dissipative rupture mode exhibited by these systems are attractive for several new applications.

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